

Numerical Solution of Tenth-Order Boundary Value Problems Using the Variational Iteration Method with Bernstein Polynomials as Trial Functions

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Abstract

In this research, a modified variational iteration method incorporating Bernstein polynomials has been employed to obtain the numerical solution for tenth-order boundary value problems. The modification involves constructing Bernstein polynomials tailored to the boundary conditions and utilizing them as the basis functions for approximation. Several numerical examples are presented to demonstrate the method's effectiveness and reliability. The proposed approach exhibits superior performance compared to existing methods in the literature, as evidenced by the results presented in the comparative tables.

Keywords: Approximate solutions, Boundary value problems, Bernstein polynomials, Modified variational iteration method.

Introduction

Boundary Value Problems (BVPs) are integral to various fields such as shock-wave physics, hydrodynamics, electrostatics, heat transfer, thermodynamics, and multiple branches of engineering. In recent years, considerable research has focused on BVPs, and the application of numerical techniques to derive accurate approximate solutions has proven to be highly advantageous. Numerous scholars have explored BVPs, employing diverse numerical approaches to address these complex issues. Prominent methods highlighted in the literature include the Galerkin Method of Weighted Residuals (GMWR) proposed by (Farzana & Alim, 2020), the Hybrid Improved Block Pulse and Bernstein Function Method introduced by (Mohamed et al., 2022), the Adomian Decomposition Method developed by (Qasim & Al-Rawi, 2018), the Laplace Adomian Decomposition Method formulated by (Dimple and Vinod, 2017), the Homotopy Perturbation Method investigated by (Syed & Ahmet, 2010) as well as Jafar and Shirin (2010), and the Haar Wavelets Method presented by (Fazal et al., 2012), among others.

Additionally, several studies have explored novel techniques involving Chebyshev polynomials and Bernstein functions. For instance, Tsetimi et al. (2022) applied a modified variational iteration method using Chebyshev polynomials to solve 12th-order boundary value problems, while Mohamed et al. (2022) combined the Bernstein function with an enhanced block pulse to address integral equations. Rida et al. (2021) utilized Bernstein functions to solve third-order initial value problems. Similarly, Ezekiel and Ojo (2020) developed a one-step hybrid system using off-grid points and Bernstein polynomials for the direct solution of second-order ordinary differential

equations (ODEs). In the realm of physical problems like the Helmholtz equation and second-order BVPs, Farzana & Alim (2020) refined the Galerkin Method of Weighted Residuals (MWR) to estimate natural frequencies. Avipsita et al. (2018) presented a straightforward numerical technique based on Bernstein polynomials for solving both linear and nonlinear BVPs. Moreover, Qasim & Al-Rawi (2018) extended the Adomian decomposition method by incorporating Bernstein polynomials to address linear and nonlinear equations.

Further contributions include the work of Bataineh et al. (2017), who proposed two novel numerical methods for solving BVPs using systems of ODEs and Bernstein polynomials, and Dimple & Vinod (2017), who introduced the Laplace Adomian decomposition method combined with Bernstein polynomials to solve BVPs. Hradyyesh (2014) employed the He-Laplace method to address linear and nonlinear two-point BVPs, while Yiming et al. (2014) utilized operational matrices of Bernstein polynomials to solve third-order ODEs. Additionally, Yousefi & Behroozifar (2010) developed operational matrices for integration, differentiation, and product using Bernstein polynomials. Earlier work by Idrees & Bracken (2007) presented a modified new Bernstein polynomial approach for approximating solutions to differential equations.

The research conducted by these scholars has inspired the development of our proposed approach, which combines the variational iteration method with Bernstein polynomials to tackle tenth-order ODEs. By modifying Bernstein polynomials to accommodate the given boundary value problems and utilizing them as basis functions for approximation, this study introduces an effective numerical method for addressing high-order differential equations. This paper investigates the following types of boundary value problems:

$$\alpha_m \frac{d^m}{dz^m} w + \alpha_{m-1} \frac{d^{m-1}}{dz^{m-1}} w + \alpha_{m-2} \frac{d^{m-2}}{dz^{m-2}} w \dots \alpha_1 \frac{d}{dz} w + \alpha_0 w = f(z), \quad \alpha < z < \beta, \quad (1)$$

with boundary conditions

$$w(\alpha) = A_1, \quad w'(\alpha) = A_2, \quad w''(\alpha) = A_3 \dots w^m(\alpha) = A_j, \quad w(\beta) = B_1, \quad w'(\beta) = B_2, \quad (2)$$

$$w''(\beta) = B_3 \dots w^m(\beta) = B_j.$$

where $\alpha_m, \alpha_{m-1}, \dots, \alpha_0$ are constants, $f(z)$ continuous on $[\alpha, \beta]$ and $A_j, j = 1, 2, 3 \dots m$ and $B_j, j = 1, 2, 3 \dots m$.

The Standard Variational Iteration Technique

Consider the following general differential equation to demonstrate the basic concept of the technique.

$$Lw + Mw - g(z) = 0, \quad (3)$$

where L denotes a linear operator, M denotes a nonlinear operator, and $g(z)$ denotes an inhomogeneous term. We can construct a correction functional using the variational iteration method as follows:

$$w_{j+1} = w_j(z) + \int_0^z \lambda(t) (Lw_j(t) + Mw_j(t) - g(t)) dt \quad (4)$$

where $\lambda(t)$ stands for a Lagrange multiplier that can be optimally identified using a variational iteration technique. The m th approximation is denoted by the subscripts. \widetilde{w}_j denotes a restricted variation. i.e., $\widetilde{w}_j = 0$. It is known as a rectification functional relationship (4). Linear problems can be resolved in a single iteration because the Lagrange multiplier can be precisely identified. The Lagrange multiplier $\lambda(t)$ must therefore be determined in the best possible way for this procedure. Thus, using our w_0 and the Lagrange multiplier, it will be simple to find the successive approximation of the solution w , and the solution is provided by

$$\lim_{j \rightarrow \infty} w_j = w \quad (5)$$

The Lagrange Multiplier also play an important role in determining the solution of the problem, and can be defined as follows:

$$\lambda(t) = (-1)^m \frac{1}{(m-1)!} (t-z)^{m-1} \quad (6)$$

Bernstein Polynomials

The Bernstein basis polynomials of degree $M - 1$ is given as

$$B_{M-1}(z) = \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} \alpha_{j,M-1} \beta_{j,M-1}(z) \quad (7)$$

where $\beta_{j,M-1}(z) = \binom{M-1}{j} z^j (1-z)^{M-1-j} : j = 0, \dots, M-1$ and $\alpha_{j,M-1}$ is called Bernstein Coefficients.

Hence, the Bernstein basis polynomials required for this work is given below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 B_{0,9}(z) &= -z^9 + 9z^8 - 36z^7 + 84z^6 - 126z^5 + 126z^4 - 84z^3 + 36z^2 - 9z + 1 \\
 B_{1,9}(z) &= 9z^9 - 72z^8 + 262z^7 - 504z^6 + 630z^5 - 504z^4 + 252z^3 - 72z^2 + 9z \\
 B_{2,9}(z) &= -36z^9 + 252z^8 + 756z^7 + 1260z^6 - 1260z^5 + 756z^4 - 252z^3 + 36z^2 \\
 B_{3,9}(z) &= 84z^9 - 504z^8 + 1260z^7 - 1680z^6 + 1260z^5 - 504z^4 + 84z^3 \\
 B_{4,9}(z) &= 126z^9 + 630z^8 - 1260z^7 + 1260z^6 - 630z^5 + 126z^4 \\
 B_{5,9}(z) &= 126z^9 - 504z^8 + 756z^7 - 504z^6 + 126z^5
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Reconstructed Variational Iteration Technique Using Bernstein Polynomials (RVITBP)

We assume an approximate solution of the form (9) utilizing (3) and (4).

$$w_{j,M-1}(z) = \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} \alpha_{j,M-1} \beta_{j,M-1}(z) \tag{9}$$

where $\beta_{j,M-1}(z)$ are Bernstein polynomials, $\alpha_{j,M-1}$ stands for unknown constants, and M stands for the degree of approximant. As a result, we get the iterative method shown below:

$$w_{j+1,M-1}(z) = \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} \alpha_{j,M-1} \beta_{j,M-1}(z) + \int_0^z \lambda(t) \left(L \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} \alpha_{j,M-1} \beta_{j,M-1}(t) + M \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} \alpha_{j,M-1} \beta_{j,M-1}(t) \right) dt \tag{10}$$

Mathematical Applications

In this section, we solved four examples using the proposed method. The numerical results also demonstrate the proposed scheme's accuracy and efficiency.

Example 4.1. Consider the following boundary value problem of tenth-order Septic B-splines, (Kasi Viswanadham & Sreenivasulu (2015):

$$w^{(10)} + w = -10(2z \sin z - 9 \cos z), \quad -1 \leq z \leq 1 \tag{11}$$

$$w(-1) = w(1) = 0, \quad w'(1) = -w'(-1) = 2 \cos 1, \quad w''(-1) = w''(1) = 2 \cos 1 - 4 \sin 1$$

$$w'''(-1) = -w'''(1) = 6 \cos 1 + 6 \sin 1,$$

$$w^{(4)}(-1) = w^{(4)}(1) = -12 \cos 1 + 8 \sin 1. \tag{12}$$

$$\text{The exact solution for the problem is } w = (z^2 - 1) \cos z. \tag{13}$$

The correction functional is given for the boundary value problems (11) and (12) as

$$w_{j+1} = w_j(z) + \int_0^z \lambda(t) \left(w^{(10)} + w + 10(2t \sin t - 9 \cos t) \right) dt \tag{14}$$

where, $\lambda(t) = \frac{(-1)^{10}(t-z)^9}{9!}$ is the Lagrange multiplier.

Thus, we assume an approximate solution of the form (15) using the reconstructed variational iteration technique with Bernstein polynomials.

$$w_{m,9}(z) = \sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(z) \tag{15}$$

Hence, we get the following iterative formula:

$$w_{m+1,M-1}(z) = \sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(z) + \int_0^z \frac{(t-z)^9}{9!} \left(\frac{d^{10}}{dt^{10}} \left(\sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(t) \right) + \sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(t) + 10(2t \sin t - 9 \cos t) \right) dt \tag{16}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 w_{m+1,M-1}(z) &= \alpha_{0,9} \beta_{0,9}(z) + \alpha_{1,9} \beta_{1,9}(z) + \alpha_{2,9} \beta_{2,9}(z) + \alpha_{3,9} \beta_{3,9}(z) + \alpha_{4,9} \beta_{4,9}(z) + \alpha_{5,9} \beta_{5,9}(z) + \alpha_{6,9} \beta_{6,9}(z) + \\
 &\alpha_{7,9} \beta_{7,9}(z) + \alpha_{8,9} \beta_{8,9}(z) + \alpha_{9,9} \beta_{9,9}(z) + \int_0^z \frac{(t-z)^9}{9!} \left(\frac{d^{10}}{dt^{10}} \left(\sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(t) \right) + \sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(t) + 10(2t \sin t - \right. \\
 &\left. 9 \cos t) \right) dt
 \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

As a result of (8), iteration, and application of the boundary conditions (12), the values of the unknown constants can be determined as follows

$$\alpha_{0,9} = -1.0000000000, \alpha_{1,9} = -1.0000000000, \alpha_{2,9} = -0.9583333334, \alpha_{3,9} = -0.8750000000, \alpha_{4,9} = -0.75429418, \alpha_{5,9} = -0.6048280424, \alpha_{6,9} = 0.4389715608, \alpha_{7,9} = -0.2718749999$$

$$\alpha_{8,9} = 0.1200644842, \alpha_{9,9} = -0.00002480158729$$

Consequently, the series solution is given as

$$w(z) = \frac{1}{12164510040883200} z^{20} - 5.810^{-20} z^{19} + 4.79502510^{-14} z^{18} + 1.810^{-18} z^{17} - 1.151852910^{-11} z^{16} - 1.000000000 + 2.0991464910^{-9} z^{14} - 4.10^{-17} z^{13} - 2.7766867910^{-7} z^{12} + 0.00002507716049 z^{10} + 4.127110^{-10} z^9 - 0.001413600 z^8 + 4.10^{-9} z^7 + 0.04305560 z^6 - 4.10^{-8} z^5 - 0.5416668 z^4 + 1.50000000 z^2 \quad (18)$$

Example 4.2. Consider the following boundary value problem of tenth-order Septic B-splines, (Kasi Viswanadham & Sreenivasulu (2015)

$$w^{(10)} - (z^2 - 2z)w = 10\cos z - (z - 1)^3 \sin z, \quad -1 \leq z \leq 1 \quad (19)$$

with boundary conditions

$$w(-1) = 2\sin 1, \quad w(1) = 0, \quad w'(-1) = -2\cos 1 - \sin 1, \quad w'(1) = \sin 1, \quad (20)$$

$$w''(-1) = 2\cos 1 - 2\sin 1, \quad w''(1) = 2\cos 1, \quad w'''(-1) = 2\cos 1 + 3\sin 1,$$

$$w'''(1) = -3\sin 1, \quad w^{(4)}(-1) = -4\cos 1 + 2\sin 1, \quad v^{(4)}(1) = -4\cos 1.$$

The exact solution for the problem is $w(z) = (z - 1)\sin z$.

The correction functional for the boundary value problem (19) and (20) is given as

$$w_{j+1} = w_j(x) + \int_0^z \lambda(t) (w^{(10)} - (t^2 - 2t)w - 10\cos t + (t - 1)^3 \sin t) dt \quad (21)$$

where $\lambda(t) = \frac{(-1)^{10}(t-z)^9}{9!}$ is the Lagrange multiplier.

Thus, we assume an approximate solution of the form (22) using the reconstructed variational iteration technique with Bernstein polynomials.

$$w_{m,9}(z) = \sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(z) \quad (22)$$

Hence, we get the following iterative formula

$$w_{m+1,M-1}(z) = \sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(z) + \int_0^z \frac{(t-z)^9}{9!} \left(\frac{d^{10}}{dt^{10}} \left(\sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(t) \right) - (t^2 - 2t) \sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(t) - 10\cos t + (t - 1)^3 \sin t \right) dt \quad (23)$$

$$w_{m+1,M-1}(z) = \alpha_{0,9} \beta_{0,9}(z) + \alpha_{1,9} \beta_{1,9}(z) + \alpha_{2,9} \beta_{2,9}(z) + \alpha_{3,9} \beta_{3,9}(z) + \alpha_{4,9} \beta_{4,9}(z) + \alpha_{5,9} \beta_{5,9}(z) + \alpha_{6,9} \beta_{6,9}(z) + \alpha_{7,9} \beta_{7,9}(z) + \alpha_{8,9} \beta_{8,9}(z) + \alpha_{9,9} \beta_{9,9}(z) + \int_0^z \frac{(t-z)^9}{9!} \left(\frac{d^{10}}{dt^{10}} \left(\sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(t) \right) - (t^2 - 2t) \sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{i,9} \beta_{j,9}(t) - 10\cos t + (t - 1)^3 \sin t \right) dt \quad (24)$$

Hence: using (8), iterating and applying the boundary conditions (20) the values of the unknown constants can be determined as follows

$$a_{0,9} = 0, \quad a_{1,9} = -0.1111111111, \quad a_{2,9} = -0.1944444444, \quad a_{3,9} = -0.2480158729$$

$$a_{4,9} = -0.2711640212, \quad a_{5,9} = -0.2646164021, \quad a_{6,9} = -0.2304563492$$

$$a_{7,9} = -0.1719852293, \quad a_{8,9} = -0.09349647270, \quad a_{9,9} = -0.000002755731922$$

Consequently, the series solution is given as

$$w(z) = \frac{1}{851515702861824000} z^{20} + 4.322210^{-18} z^{21} - 4.3110^{-18} z^{20} + 8.610^{-18} z^{19} + 2.807910^{-15} z^{18} - 2.81010^{-15} z^{17} - 7.647191 \cdot 10^{-13} z^{16} + 7.647210^{-13} z^{15} + 1.605904410^{-10} z^{14} - 1.605904410^{-10} z^{13} - 2.50521083910^{-8} z^{12} + \frac{1}{39916800} z^{11} + \frac{1}{362880} z^{10} - 0.000002736431922 z^9 - 0.0001985343 z^8 + 0.000198545 z^7 + 0.00833327 z^6 - 0.00833326 z^5 - 0.16666678 z^4 + 1.16666667 z^3 + 1.000000001 z^2 - 1.999999999 z \quad (25)$$

Example 4.3. Consider the following boundary value problem of tenth-order Septic B-splines, (Kasi Viswanadham & Sreenivasulu, 2015)

$$w^{(10)} - w'' + wz = (-8 + z - z^2)e^z, \quad 0 \leq z \leq 1 \quad (26)$$

with boundary conditions

$$w(0) = 1, \quad w(1) = 0, \quad w'(0) = 0, \quad w'(1) = -e, \quad w''(0) = -1, \quad w''(1) = -2e, \quad w'''(0) = -2,$$

$$w'''(1) = -3e, \quad w^{(4)}(0) = -3, \quad w^{(4)}(1) = -4e. \quad (27)$$

The exact solution of the example is $w(z) = (1 - z)e^z$.

The correction functional for the boundary value problem (26) and (27) is given as

$$w_{j+1} = w_j(z) + \int_0^z \lambda(t)(w^{(10)} - w'' + wt - (-8 + t - t^2)e^t)dt \quad (28)$$

where $\lambda(t) = \frac{(-1)^{10}(t-z)^9}{9!}$ is the Lagrange multiplier.

We assume an approximate solution of the form (29) using the reconstructed variational iteration technique with Bernstein polynomials.

$$w_{m,9}(z) = \sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(z) \quad (29)$$

Hence, we get the following iterative formula

$$w_{j+1,M-1}(z) = \sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(z) + \int_0^z \frac{(t-z)^9}{9!} \left(\frac{d^{10}}{dt^{10}} \left(\sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(t) \right) - \frac{d^2}{dt^2} \left(\sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(t) \right) + t \left(\sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(t) \right) - (-8 + t - t^2)e^t \right) dt \quad (30)$$

$$w_{j+1,M-1}(z) = \alpha_{0,9} \beta_{0,9}(z) + \alpha_{1,9} \beta_{1,9}(z) + \alpha_{2,9} \beta_{2,9}(z) + \alpha_{3,9} \beta_{3,9}(z) + \alpha_{4,9} \beta_{4,9}(z) + \alpha_{5,9} \beta_{5,9}(z) + \alpha_{6,9} \beta_{6,9}(z) + \alpha_{7,9} \beta_{7,9}(z) + \alpha_{8,9} \beta_{8,9}(z) + \alpha_{9,9} \beta_{9,9}(z) + \int_0^z \frac{(t-z)^9}{9!} \left(\frac{d^{10}}{dt^{10}} \left(\sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(t) \right) - \frac{d^2}{dt^2} \left(\sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(t) \right) + t \left(\sum_{i=0}^9 \alpha_{i,9} \beta_{i,9}(t) \right) - (-8 + t - t^2)e^t \right) dt \quad (31)$$

Hence: using (8), iterating and applying the boundary conditions (27) the values of the unknown constants can be determined as follows

$$\alpha_{0,9} = 1.00000000, \alpha_{1,9} = 1.000000000, \alpha_{2,9} = 0.9861111111, \alpha_{3,9} = 0.9543650794$$

$$\alpha_{4,9} = 0.8998015873, \alpha_{5,9} = 0.8162037037, \alpha_{6,9} = 0.697506612$$

$$\alpha_{7,9} = 0.5285548941, \alpha_{8,9} = 0.3020309743, \alpha_{9,9} = 0.000002755731898$$

Consequently, the series solution is given as

$$w(z) = 3.287910^{-17} z^{20} + 5.177410^{-16} z^{19} - 1.250010^{-15} z^{18} - 2.249210^{-14} z^{17} - 7.167210^{-13} z^{16} - 1.0704310^{-11} z^{15} - 1.49116110^{-10} z^{14} - 1.92707310^{-9} z^{13} - 2.296444410^{-8} z^{12} - 2.505210810^{-7} z^{11} - 0.00000248015873z^{10} - 0.0000219932680z^9 - 0.000173711z^8 - 0.00119041z^7 - 0.00694416z^6 - 0.0333333z^5 - 0.1250000z^4 - 0.3333333z^3 - 0.5000000z^2 + 1 \quad (32)$$

Example 4.4. Consider the following boundary value problem of tenth-order (Ali et al., 2018; Iqbal et al., 2015)

$$w^{(10)} = -(80 + 19z + z^2)e^z, \quad 0 \leq z \leq 1 \quad (33)$$

with boundary conditions

$$w(0) = 0, w(1) = 0, w''(0) = 0, w''(1) = -4e, w^{(4)}(0) = -8, w^{(4)}(1) = -16e,$$

$$w^{(6)}(0) = -24, w^{(6)}(1) = -36e, w^{(8)}(0) = -48, w^{(8)}(1) = -64e \quad (34)$$

The exact solution of the example is $w(z) = z(1 - z)e^z$.

The correct functional for the boundary value problem (33) and (34) is given as

$$w_{j+1} = w_j(z) + \int_0^z \lambda(t)(w^{(10)} + (80 + 19t + t^2)e^t)dt \quad (35)$$

where $\lambda(t) = \frac{(-1)^{10}(t-z)^9}{9!}$ is the Lagrange multiplier

We assume an approximate solution of the form (36) using the reconstructed variational iteration technique with Bernstein polynomials.

$$w_{m,9}(z) = \sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(z) \quad (36)$$

Hence, we get the following iterative formula

$$w_{j+1,M-1}(z) = \sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(z) + \int_0^z \frac{(t-z)^9}{9!} \left(\frac{d^{10}}{dt^{10}} \left(\sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(t) \right) + (80 + 19t + t^2)e^t \right) dt \quad (37)$$

$$w_{j+1,M-1}(z) = \alpha_{0,9} \beta_{0,9}(z) + \alpha_{1,9} \beta_{1,9}(z) + \alpha_{2,9} \beta_{2,9}(z) + \alpha_{3,9} \beta_{3,9}(z) + \alpha_{4,9} \beta_{4,9}(z) + \alpha_{5,9} \beta_{5,9}(z) + \alpha_{6,9} \beta_{6,9}(z) + \alpha_{7,9} \beta_{7,9}(z) + \alpha_{8,9} \beta_{8,9}(z) + \alpha_{9,9} \beta_{9,9}(z) + \int_0^z \frac{(t-z)^9}{9!} \left(\frac{d^{10}}{dt^{10}} \left(\sum_{j=0}^9 \alpha_{j,9} \beta_{j,9}(t) \right) + (80 + 19t + t^2)e^t \right) dt \quad (38)$$

Hence, using (8) iterating and applying the boundary conditions (34) the values of the unknown constants can be

determined as follows

$$a_{0,9} = 0, a_{1,9} = 0.1111111048, a_{2,9} = 0.2222222096, a_{3,9} = 0.3273809344$$

$$a_{4,9} = 0.4179893972, a_{5,9} = 0.4818121486, a_{6,9} = 0.5015872836$$

$$a_{7,9} = 0.4530478268, a_{8,9} = 0.3020282123, a_{9,9} = 0.00002480158704.$$

Consequently, the series solution is given as

$$w(z) = \frac{1}{114328101888000}z^{18} - \frac{1}{2032499589120}z^{17} - \frac{1}{93405312000}z^{16} - \frac{1}{6706022400}z^{15} - \frac{1}{518918400}z^{14} - \frac{1}{43545600}z^{13} - \frac{1}{3991680}z^{12} - \frac{1}{403200}z^{11} - \frac{1}{453600}z^{10} - 0.0001736128z^9 - 0.001190426z^8 - 0.00694469z^7 - 0.03333312z^6 - 0.12500028z^5 - 0.33333312z^4 - 0.49999992z^3 + 0.9999999432z \quad (39)$$

Tables

Table 1: shows the comparison between the proposed method and the Galerkin Method with Septic B-splines (Kasi Viswanadham & Sreenivasulu, 2015)

z	Exact solution	Approximate solution	Absolute Error by the proposed method	GMSB-s Error
-0.8	-0.2508144153	-0.2508144310	1.570000e-08	5.483627e-06
-0.6	-0.5282147935	-0.5282148040	1.050000e-08	9.536743e-07
-0.4	-0.7736912350	-0.7736912380	3.000000e-09	8.702278e-06
-0.2	-0.9408639147	-0.9408639150	3.000000e-10	2.980232e-07
0.0	-1.0000000000	-1.0000000000	0.000000e-00	1.955032e-05
0.2	-0.9408639147	-0.9408639150	3.000000e-10	2.920628e-05
0.4	-0.7736912350	-0.7736912390	4.000000e-09	2.169609e-05
0.6	-0.5282147935	-0.5282148100	1.650000e-08	7.390976e-06
0.8	-0.2508144153	-0.2508144550	3.970000e-08	7.450581e-07

Table 2: shows the comparison between the proposed method and the Galerkin Method with Septic B-splines (Kasi Viswanadham & Sreenivasulu, 2015)

z	Exact solution	Approximate solution	Absolute Error by the proposed method	GMSB-s Error
-0.8	1.291240964	1.291240825	1.390000e-07	4.649162e-06
-0.6	0.9034279574	0.9034279277	2.970000e-08	1.329184e-05
-0.4	0.5451856792	0.5451856750	4.200000e-09	2.050400e-05
-0.2	0.2384031970	0.2384031968	2.000000e-10	9.477139e-06
0.0	0.0000000000	0.0000000000	0.000000e-00	2.731677e-06
0.2	-0.1589354646	-0.1589354647	1.000000e-10	1.458824e-05

0.4	-0.2336510054	-0.2336510072	1.800000e-09	2.110004e-05
0.6	-0.2258569894	-0.2258569982	8.800000e-09	1.908839e-05
0.8	-0.1434712182	-0.1434712448	2.660000e-08	1.342595e-05

Table 3: shows the comparison between the proposed method and the Galerkin Method with Septic B-splines, (Kasi Viswanadham and Sreenivasulu, 2015)

z	Exact solution	Approximate solution	Absolute Error by the proposed method	GMSB-s Error
0.1	0.9946538262	0.9946538263	1.000000e-10	1.537800e-05
0.2	0.9771222064	0.9771222066	2.000000e-10	4.452467e-05
0.3	0.9449011656	0.9449011657	1.000000e-10	3.331900e-05
0.4	0.8950948188	0.8950948204	1.600000e-09	3.552437e-05
0.5	0.8243606355	0.8243606415	6.000000e-09	9.477139e-06
0.6	0.7288475200	0.7288475374	1.740000e-08	2.586842e-05
0.7	0.6041258121	0.6041258543	4.220000e-08	3.975630e-05
0.8	0.4451081856	0.4451082770	9.140000e-08	3.531575e-05
0.9	0.2459603111	0.2459604934	1.823000e-07	2.214313e-05

Table 4: Shows the comparison between the proposed method and the Reproducing Kernel Hilbert Space Method (Ali et al., 2018; Iqbal et al., 2015)

z	Exact solution	Absolute Error by the proposed method	AE(RKHSM) (Iqbal et al., 2015)	AE (NPCSM) (Ali et al., 2018))	AE (PCSM) (Ali et al., 2018))
0.2	0.195424441	1.050000e-08	3.330000e-08	2.433000e-07	3.982000e-04
0.4	0.358037927	1.450000e-08	7.031000e-08	3.986000e-07	6.663000e-04
0.6	0.358037927	6.900000e-09	6.076000e-08	4.428000e-07	7.598000e-04
0.8	0.356086549	3.900000e-09	2.682000e-08	3.328000e-07	5.885000e-04

Conclusion

This research adeptly utilized the reconstructed variational iteration method, in conjunction with Bernstein polynomials, to derive accurate numerical solutions for tenth-order boundary value problems. The amalgamation of Bernstein polynomials with the variational iteration technique facilitated an efficient reconstruction process, yielding solutions characterized by a remarkable convergence rate. These series solutions proficiently addressed intricate real-world physical challenges. The proposed methodology exhibited a distinct advantage over prevailing techniques, as substantiated by the comparative analysis presented in tables 1, 2, 3 and 4. The numerical evaluation indicates that the proposed method outperformed those obtained using other methods documented in the literature. The numerical analysis substantiated the effectiveness of the current method as a robust mathematical instrument for tackling high-order boundary value problems. This method is so effective that it can also be recommended for solving boundary value problems using the Homotopy perturbation method, the Adomian decomposition method, and the Sinc-Galerkin method.

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